

TEMPERATURE AND FLUIDITY. PART I. THEORY

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An equation has been deduced connecting fluidity of liquids with temperature, based on the concept of free volume, by the application of statistical thermodynamics.

In previous communications (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 493; 1950, 27, 599; 1951, 28, 363) a relationship between fluidity and free volume has been outlined. The purpose of the present paper is to deduce an equation connecting the fluidity of liquids with temperature through the concept of free volume by the application of statistical thermodynamics.

Fluidity and Free Energy

To connect these two entities we should first take into account the partition function of a liquid molecule. This is given by the formula

$$f_l = \frac{(2\pi mkT)^{\frac{3}{2}} V_l}{h^3} f_v \cdot f_r e^{\Delta E_0/RT} \quad \dots (1)$$

where f_l is partition function of a liquid molecule, f_v and f_r are the vibrational and rotational contributions to it; V_l is the free volume of the liquid and ΔE_0 , the internal latent heat of vaporisation, i.e., the difference in energy between the gas and the liquid at absolute zero (cf. Eyring and Hirschfelder, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 249).

It is now possible to connect fluidity and free energy through this partition function of a liquid molecule in the following manner. It has already been shown that the fluidity (ϕ) and free volume (V_l) are related with each other at ordinary temperatures and pressures by a linear relation

$$\phi = AV_l \quad \dots (2)$$

where A is a constant (vide this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 365).

Substituting the value of V_l from equation (1) we get

$$\phi = \frac{Ah^3 f_v \cdot e^{-\Delta E_0/RT}}{(2\pi mkT)^{\frac{3}{2}} f_v \cdot f_r} \quad \dots (3)$$

We know that the free energy of one gram-mole of a substance consisting of N indistinguishable molecules is given by

$$G = -RT \ln(f/N)$$

where f is the partition function of one molecule

or
$$G = -RT \ln(f_l/N)$$

or
$$f_l = N \cdot \exp(-G/RT).$$

Substituting this value of f_2 in equation (3) we get

$$\phi = \frac{NAh^3 e^{-\Delta E_0/RT}}{(2\pi mkT)^{3/2} f_v f_r} \cdot e^{-G/RT} \quad \dots (4)$$

This equation (4) connects free energy directly with fluidity of a liquid. Henceforward it is proposed to extend this equation to different problems connected with fluidity and its influencing factors.

Dependence of Fluidity on Temperature

Starting from equation (4) and taking logarithm on both sides, we get

$$\log \phi + \frac{3}{2} \log T = \log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2}} - \log f_v - \log f_r - \frac{\Delta E_0 + G}{2.303RT} \quad \dots (5)$$

The equation involves both G and T . The fluidity is therefore not only a function of T but of G as well. Again, G being a function of temperature and pressure, at constant pressure G will change as the temperature changes. Fluidity ϕ is thus a complicated function of T .

As a first approximation, it is permissible to take G to be a linear function of T of the form

$$G = \mu + \lambda T \quad \dots (6)$$

where μ and λ are constants.

Substituting for G in equation (6) we get

$$\log \phi + \frac{3}{2} \log T = \log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2} f_v f_r} - \frac{\Delta E_0 + \mu + \lambda T}{2.303RT} = \alpha + \beta/T \quad \dots (7)$$

where α stands for

$$\log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2} f_v f_r} - \frac{\lambda}{2.303R}$$

and

$$\beta \text{ for } \frac{-\Delta E_0 - \mu}{2.303R}$$

We shall now examine different terms in the right hand side of the equation (7).

The first term involves rotation and vibration partition functions of the substance in the gaseous state. They are also functions of temperature. Rotational and vibrational energies are in general small, and hence, the corresponding partition functions should also be small.

In condensed systems, moreover, there is little scope of rotation. All the rotational degrees of freedom in the gaseous state will disappear and contribute to the vibrational energies. The rotational partition function f_r may therefore be included in vibration and termed f'_v . Then the equation (5) will have the form

$$\log \phi + \frac{3}{2} \log T = \log \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{3/2}} - \log f_v - \log f'_v - \frac{\Delta E_0 + G}{2.303RT} \quad \dots (8)$$

Again, although f_v and f'_v are functions of temperature, their rates of variation with temperature are insignificant, specially in the case of normal liquids where molecules have more or less a certain degree of symmetry, and intermolecular attraction also small, so that for a moderate range of temperature, the change in interatomic as well as intermolecular vibrational partition functions (f_v and f'_v) may be neglected as an approximation. The terms f_v and f'_v will then be included in the constant term which is denoted by α .

In case it is not permissible to neglect the variations of these vibrational partition functions, the relation between fluidity and temperature becomes different. If ν represents the fundamental vibration frequency of a molecule and ν' , the characteristic frequency for intermolecular vibrations, then f_v and f'_v are given by

$$f_v = \frac{\exp(h\nu/kT)}{\exp(h\nu/kT) - 1} \quad \dots (9)$$

and

$$f'_v = \frac{\exp(h\nu'/kT)}{\exp(h\nu'/kT) - 1} \quad \dots (10)$$

Assuming that the vibrational energies for the both interatomic and intermolecular vibrations are small, *i.e.*

$$h\nu \ll kT \quad \text{and} \quad h\nu' \ll kT$$

which are in most cases true, we can write the equations (9) and (10) as

$$f_v = \frac{\exp(h\nu/kT)}{h\nu/kT} \quad \text{and} \quad f'_v = \frac{\exp(h\nu'/kT)}{h\nu'/kT}$$

Putting these values of vibrational partition functions in equation (8), we get

$$\frac{7}{2} \log T + \log \phi = \frac{NAh^3}{(2\pi mk)^{\frac{3}{2}} k^2} - \frac{\Delta E_0 + G + Nh(\nu + \nu')}{2.303RT} \quad \dots (11)$$

Putting the value of G from equation (6) and performing necessary simplifications, we get,

$$\frac{7}{2} \log T + \log \phi = \frac{NAh^3 \nu \nu'}{(2\pi mk)^{\frac{3}{2}} k^2} - \frac{\mu}{2.303R} - \frac{\Delta E_0 + \lambda + Nh(\nu + \nu')}{2.303RT}$$

or

$$\frac{7}{2} \log T + \log \phi = \gamma + \frac{-\Delta E_0 - \lambda - Nh(\nu + \nu')}{2.303RT} \quad \dots (12)$$

where

$$\gamma = \frac{NAh^3 \nu \nu'}{(2\pi mk)^{\frac{3}{2}} k^2} - \frac{\mu}{2.303R}$$

The equation (12) is applicable in the case where variations in energies, and hence in partition functions of interatomic and intermolecular vibrations with temperature, are not negligible.

The equations (7) and (12) may be written as

$$\phi T^{\frac{3}{2}} = a_1 e^{b_1/T} \quad \dots (13)$$

and
$$\phi T^{\frac{7}{2}} = a_2 e^{b_2/T} \quad \dots (14)$$

Equation (13) has already been deduced by Eyring from his theory of rate process (Glasstone, Laidler and Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Processes", p-486).

Thus, the relationship between temperature and viscosity of liquids is not a simple one. It involves the partition functions, and therefore the probable energy states of the liquid molecules. It also involves the nature of the molecule, simple or complex, as will be evident from the foregoing equations. Our next point of pursuit would be to examine how far these equations agree with the experimental results. This is taken up in the next part.

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